

1
2
3
4
5 1 **ACA-20-2164-Rev.Highlighted**
6
7

8
9 2 **Exploring the potential of combining**
10
11
12
13 3 **chemometric approaches to model non-linear**
14
15
16
17 4 **multi-way data with quantitative purposes – A**
18
19
20
21
22 5 **case study**
23
24
25
26
27 6
28
29

30 7 Mónica Palomino Vasco¹, Nielene M. Mora Díaz¹, María I. Rodríguez-Cáceres¹, María I. Acedo-
31 8 Valenzuela¹, Mirta R. Alcaraz^{2,3,*} and Héctor C. Goicoechea^{2,3}
32
33 9

34
35
36
37 10 ¹*Department of Analytical Chemistry and Research Institute on Water, Climate Change and*
38 11 *Sustainability (IACYS), University of Extremadura, Badajoz, 06006, Spain*
39 12

40 13 ²*Laboratorio de Desarrollo Analítico y Quimiometría (LADAQ), Cátedra de Química Analítica*
41 14 *I, Facultad de Bioquímica y Ciencias Biológicas, Universidad Nacional del Litoral, Ciudad*
42 15 *Universitaria, Santa Fe (S3000ZAA), Argentina*
43 16

44 17 ³*Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas (CONICET), Godoy Cruz 2290*
45 18 *CABA (C1425FQB), Argentina.*
46
47 19
48
49

50 20
51
52 21

Corresponding author:

53 22 *E-mail: malcaraz@fbc.unl.edu.ar (M.R. Alcaraz). Tel.: +54 342 4575206 x190
54
55 23
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1
2
3
4 **24 Abstract**

5
6 25 Second-order based calibration methods have been widely investigated capitalizing on the
7
8
9 26 inherent benefits of the data structure and the decomposition models, demonstrating that second-
10
11 27 order advantage is a property that conspires to a high likelihood success in the resolution of
12
13
14 28 systems of varying complexity. This work aims to demonstrate the applicability of a combined
15
16 29 chemometric strategy to solve non-linear multivariate calibration systems in the presence of non-
17
18
19 30 multilinear multi-way data. The determination of histamine by differential pulse voltammetry at
20
21 31 different pH is presented as case study. The experimental system has the outstanding difficulty
22
23
24 32 arisen from the large displacement along the potential axis by the pH, which was successfully
25
26 33 overcome by implementation of the presented combined strategy. For data modeling, MCR-ALS,
27
28
29 34 U-PLS/RBL and U-PCA/RBL-RBF were used. MCR-ALS allowed unraveling the non-linear
30
31 35 behavior between the signal and the concentration, and extracting the underlying profiles of the
32
33
34 36 constituent. Quantitative analysis was performed through the three models, and a comparative
35
36 37 evaluation of the predictive performance was done. The best results were achieved with U-
37
38
39 38 PCA/RBL-RBF (mean recovery= 101%) whereas, MCR-ALS yield the lowest mean recovery for
40
41 39 all samples (70%)

42
43
44
45
46
47 41
48
49
50
51 42 *Keywords:* non-trilinear type 3 data; pH-voltammetry; non-linear regression model; MCR-ALS;
52
53
54 43 U-PLS/RBL; ANNs
55
56
57
58 44

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

45 1. Introduction

46 Multivariate calibration techniques have been attracting the attention of researchers in
47 several investigation fields. The interest in the use of multivariate analysis relies on the fact that
48 the inclusion of multiple signals can significantly improve the applicability of quantitative
49 analyses [1, 2].

50 The central purpose of multivariate calibration is to establish empirical models relating
51 unselective multiple instrumental signals to known analyte concentrations, which are then
52 utilized to predict the analyte concentration of the test sample [3]. The multivariate calibration
53 methodologies are categorized into first-, second- or higher-order calibration in association to the
54 instrumental modes of the acquired signal [4, 5]. One particularity of first-order calibration
55 methods is the requirement of a large number of calibration samples that must contain similar
56 composition than the target sample, i.e., to contain the same potential interferents, for the success
57 of the resolution and the prediction [3]. Nonetheless, second- and higher-order calibration
58 models outweigh this attribute through a property that enables to selectively identify the
59 components of a mixture even in the presence of non-modeled constituents, which is universally
60 known as “second-order advantage” [5, 6].

61 The evolution of the modern analytical instrumentation has facilitated the acquisition of
62 multidimensional signals allowing to enlarge the chemical information that can be obtained from
63 the system under study. Some of the most common analytical instruments can yield first-order
64 data for a single sample (e.g., infrared spectrum [7], UV spectrum [8], DSC signals [9]), which
65 are acquired as a unidimensional vector data array. Second-order data could be obtained with a
unique instrument, but it can be generated by instrumental hyphenation or experimental setups,
allowing arranging the signals in bidimensional data arrays, i.e., data matrix. For instance,

1
2
3
4 68 excitation-emission fluorescence matrices [10], chromatography coupled to spectral detection
5
6
7 69 [11] and kinetic with spectral monitoring [12] are cases of second-order data acquisition.
8

9 70 In the literature, it is possible to find several techniques for multivariate quantitative
10
11 71 analysis. Notwithstanding this great diversity of methods offers exceptional versatility in the
12
13
14 72 development of quantitative models, it usually leaves the analyst uncertain as to which is the
15
16 73 most appropriate for a given set of data. This situation is not a trivial matter since each data set
17
18
19 74 comprises particular underlying factors, e.g., noise level, signal overlapping, among others, that
20
21 75 cannot be generalized. One of the underlying factors of the data that must be considered before
22
23
24 76 modeling is the data linearity. In this regard, it becomes necessary to make a distinction between
25
26 77 the types of linearity that can be observed in the multivariate calibration field.
27

28
29 78 First, it should be evaluated if the instrumental modes in which the data was collected are
30
31 79 mutually independent. This condition guarantees the concept of *multi-linearity* of the multiway
32
33 80 data. When lack of multi-linearity is observed, it is relevant to identify its origin to evaluate the
34
35
36 81 different strategies that can be implemented for the resolution. The lack of multi-linearity has
37
38 82 been well described elsewhere by Olivieri and Escandar, who introduced a classification for the
39
40
41 83 different types of non-linearity in three- and four-way data structures [4]. On the other hand, in
42
43 84 analytical chemistry, many quantitative procedures apply linear calibration models to describe
44
45 85 the relationship between the instrumental measurement (dependent variable) and the property of
46
47
48 86 interest (independent variable) [13]. However, there are systems in which the linear law is not
49
50
51 87 obeyed, e.g., violation of the Beer-Lambert law, and non-linear functions ought to be applied to
52
53 88 fit the data. Hence, the evaluation of the lack of linearity and multi-linearity is an unavoidable
54
55 89 start in any multivariate quantitative procedure.
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

90 Among calibration models, partial least square (PLS), principal component analysis
91 (PCA) or classical least square (CLS) are the most common algorithms [13] for first-order
92 calibration methods, while unfolded-PLS and multi-way-PLS (U-PLS and N-PLS) are two of the
93 used algorithms in second-order calibration procedures [14]. All these algorithms perform linear
94 calibration models, i.e., linear regression modeling, and only data that conform to the principle of
95 multi-linearity can be subjected to decomposition [13, 15]. Besides, parallel factor analysis
96 (PARAFAC) [16] and multivariate curve resolution coupled to alternating least-squares (MCR-
97 ALS) [17] are algorithms based on alternating least-square optimization that allows decomposing
98 higher-order data and gathering *loadings*, which comprise the individual profiles of the
99 constituents, and *scores*, that are the contribution of the analytes in each sample [18]. The
100 obtained scores can be then utilized to build the proper regression model in predictive studies,
101 even in systems where the analytical signals do not vary linearly with the analyte concentration.
102 However, when the non-linear relationship between the dependent and the independent variable
103 is present, artificial neural networks (ANNs) are the most common methods used in building the
104 empirical non-linear calibration model [19]. ANNs are non-parametric techniques, so they do not
105 assume any specific model form providing them with especial flexibility and ability to model
106 diverse kind of data [20].

107 This work aims to demonstrate the applicability of a combined chemometric strategy to
108 solve non-linear multivariate calibration systems in the presence of lack of multi-linearity in
109 multi-way data. In this research, the quantitation of histamine in the presence of histidine by
110 differential pulse voltammetry at different pH is presented as case study. These data represent an
111 outstanding chemometrics challenge because of the large potential-displacements of the
112 electroanalytical signal arisen from the pH variation. Moreover, for the best of our knowledge,

1
2
3
4 113 no reports regarding second-order DPV-pH data coupled to chemometrics with quantitative aims
5
6 114 have been published yet.

7
8
9 115

10 11 116 **2. Experimental section**

12 13 14 117 *2.1. Chemical, reagents and samples*

15
16 118 Histamine (HIM) and histidine (HIS) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Stenheim,
17
18 Germany) and Fluka (Buchs, Switzerland), respectively. Boric acid (p.a. H_3BO_3) was obtained
19 119 from Merk (Darmstadt, Germany). Glacial acetic acid (HAc), *o*-phosphoric acid (H_3PO_4),
20
21 120 sodium hydroxide (NaOH) and dimethylformamide (DMF), all of analytical grade, were
22
23 121 acquired from Panreac (Barcelona, Spain). Ultra-pure water was obtained with a Milli-Q
24
25 122 purification system from Millipore (Bedford, USA).
26
27
28
29 123

30
31 124 Analytes stock solutions of 500 mg L^{-1} were prepared by dissolution of the appropriate
32
33 125 amount of the powder presentation in ultrapure water and stored under refrigeration in the dark.
34
35
36 126 Britton-Robinson Buffer (BRB) was prepared by mixing the proper amount of H_3BO_3 , HAc and
37
38 127 H_3PO_4 , in order to obtain a final concentration of 40 mmol L^{-1} of each substance. To perform the
39
40 128 pH-dependent experiments, the pH of the BRB was adjusted with NaOH, as appropriate, prior to
41
42 129 the sample preparation.
43
44
45

46 130

47 48 131 *2.2. Calibration and validation samples*

49
50 132 A calibration set of HIM pure standard sample was daily prepared in triplicate by
51
52 133 transferring the proper aliquot of the analyte stock solutions and 2.0 mL of BRB of the
53
54 134 corresponding pH to a 10.00 mL volumetric flask and completing to the mark with ultra-pure
55
56
57 135 water. The final HIM concentrations were ranging between 0.0 and 10.0 mg mL^{-1} .
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

136 A sample validation set was built considering HIM concentrations different than those used
137 for the calibration samples. In these samples, HIS was incorporated as non-modeled interferent
138 in 3 different concentrations as detailed in Table 1. The validation samples were prepared as
139 previously described for the calibration samples.

141 2.3. Instrumentation and experimental procedure

142 Differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) measurements were conducted using a Metrohm
143 663 VA and an AUTOLAB PGSTAT 10 potentiostat/galvanostat (ECOChemie. Utrecht, The
144 Netherlands) with General-Purpose Electrochemical software (GPES) version 4.9.006
145 (ECOChemie. Utrecht, The Netherlands) for the data acquisition and instrument control.

146 The DPV experiments were carried out in a 10 mL cell using a conventional three-
147 electrode system configuration including a 3.0 mm diameter glassy carbon electrode (GCE) as
148 working electrode, an Ag/AgCl (saturated KCl) reference electrode and a 0.3 mm platinum wire
149 auxiliary electrode, all of them commercially acquired (ECOChemie. Utrecht, The Netherlands).

150 At the beginning of the working day, the surface of the GCE was mechanically cleaned
151 using a cotton pad soaked in DMF for 2 minutes and in ultrapure water for 30 seconds. Then, an
152 electrochemical cleaning was made by applying three reduction cycles in the range of +1.5 –
153 +0.9 V, at 15 mV s⁻¹, with an amplitude of 0.05 V, to the supporting electrolyte solution. The
154 supporting electrolyte solution consisted in a BRB solution adjusted at the appropriate
155 experimental pH. After electrode conditioning, DPV measurements were conducted by scanning
156 the potential range of +0.9 V to +1.5 V at a scanning rate of 15 mV s⁻¹, with an amplitude of
157 0.05 V. Between measurements, the surface of the electrode was regenerated through mechanical
158 cleaning. All experiments were carried out at room temperature.

1
2
3
4 159 For the pH measurements, a Crison Micro pH 501m (Barcelona, Spain) equipped with a
5
6
7 160 combined glass/saturated calomel electrode, was used.
8

9 161 10 11 162 *2.4. Software* 12 13

14 163 Data processing and analysis were performed in MATLAB 2015b [21]. MCR-ALS GUI
15
16 164 2.0 [22] codes for MATLAB were freely downloaded from www.mcr-als.info. U-PLS/RBL and
17
18
19 165 U-PCA-RBL-RBF were implemented in MVC2 [23] and MVC1 [24], respectively, for which the
20
21 166 MATLAB codes are available at <http://www.iquir-conicet.gov.ar/eng/div5.php?area=12>. *i-*
22
23
24 167 coshift [25-27] tool for MATLAB was acquired from <http://www.models.life.ku.dk/icoshift>.
25

26 168 For baseline correction, a moving average procedure (peak width of 0.01), which is
27
28
29 169 available in the GEPS software, was implemented (Figure S1).
30

31 170 32 33 171 **3. Results and discussion** 34

35 36 172 *3.1. General considerations* 37

38 173 *3.1.1. Chemometrics in electroanalytical chemistry* 39

40
41 174 Curiously, the number of publications reporting the use of chemometrics in
42
43 175 electrochemistry is small in comparison with the application of other analytical methodologies,
44
45
46 176 such as spectroscopy or chromatography. This observation has been recently stated by Esteban *et*
47
48 177 *al.* in Ref [28] whose proposed the hypothesis that the dearth of research in this topic might be
49
50
51 178 caused by the close relationship between mathematics and electrochemistry and, also, the lack of
52
53 179 linearity between the signal and the concentration of the electroactive species [29, 30].
54
55 180 Nevertheless, there is an ongoing interest in exploit the potentialities of electrochemical
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1
2
3
4 181 instrumentation by applying chemometrics and promote its use to solve electroanalytical
5
6 182 problems.

7
8
9 183 First-order calibration methods have been extensively used in electroanalytical chemistry
10
11 184 by the implementation of the classical calibration models as multi-linear regression (MLR), PLS
12
13 185 or PCR, among others [30]. Moreover, higher-order calibration methods have been recently
14
15 186 explored and presented in several publications reporting the application of MCR-ALS, PLS-
16
17 187 based methods and ANNs techniques for the predictive analysis of compounds in samples of
18
19 188 variate nature [31, [32](#)]. Among the electroanalytical techniques, differential pulse voltammetry
20
21 189 (DPV) and stripping voltammetry (SP) are the most used for the acquisition of second-order data
22
23 190 with quantitative aims [29, 31, 33, 34]. However, some features inherent to the electrochemical
24
25 191 systems are cumbersome and made difficult the direct implementation of a chemometric model.
26
27 192 One of the most common issues present in electrochemistry is the signal displacement by
28
29 193 empirical phenomena that leads to a lack of linearity of the signal-analyte concentration
30
31 194 relationship and a loss of multi-linearity in the multi-way data. Hence, recent works are focused
32
33 195 on the development of new strategies that enable either the modeling of non-linear data [34] or
34
35 196 the correction of shifted data [29, [35](#), [36](#)]. Nevertheless, there is a noticeable dearth of research in
36
37 197 this field when large signal-shifts occur, for example, as it is the case of the displacement along
38
39 198 the potential axis of some irreversible signals as a function of the pH [29].
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47

48 199

50 200 *3.2. Data properties*

53 201 *3.2.1. Multi-linearity*

55 202 When second-order data are obtained for a set of samples, the data matrices can be
56
57 203 organized into a three-way structure, which can whether conform to the *low-rank trilinearity*
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

204 principle (henceforth referred to as trilinearity) or not. In this case, it is appropriate to be referred
205 to the classification tree for a three-way data of a set of samples proposed by Olivieri and
206 Escandar elsewhere [4]. Briefly, four types of data are distinguished according to the trilinearity
207 concept: 1) *trilinear*; 2) *non-trilinear type 1*; 3) *non-trilinear type 2*; and *non-trilinear type 3* (for
208 more details, the reader must be referred to Ref [4]). The latter corresponds to the case when
209 individual second-order data do not conform to the bilinearity principle. It should be highlighted
210 that the most of the experimental second-order calibration investigations reported in the literature
211 have performed the acquisition and modeling of trilinear three-way data set or non-trilinear type
212 1 three-way data. Furthermore, a small number of publications report calibration methods built
213 with non-bilinear data modeling with quantitative purposes, i.e., non-trilinear type 3 data [37,
214 38].

215 The experimental data presented in this report consist of a set of second-order data
216 comprising the DPV signals of HIM at six different pH (DPV-pH). Figure 1.A depicts the DPV-
217 pH second-order data of HIM at a given concentration, while Fig. 1.B shows the DPV signals
218 acquired for different concentrations of HIM at the same pH (pH 6). In Fig. 1.A, it is clear to
219 observe that the DPV-pH matrix presents severe deviations of bilinearity as result of the
220 displacement of the oxidation peak potential with the pH: *the HIM peak shifts negatively with*
221 *rising the pH value*, in agreement with previous reports [39]. Additionally, a significant shift
222 between DPV signals arisen from the different concentrations at the same pH is observable
223 (Fig. 1.B).

225 ***** Figure 1 *****

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

227 These observations lead to the conclusion that the multi-way data set, i.e., DPV-pH-
228 concentration, is a severe case of non-trilinear type 3 data, since neither bilinearity in the DPV-
229 pH nor bilinearity in the DPV-concentration arrays are fulfilled. It is worth to highlight that this
230 is the first time that this type of non-trilinear data is used with quantitative purposes.

231 Under this complex scenario, several alternatives were implemented to carry out the
232 chemometric modeling. After an in-depth evaluation of the possible strategies, the following
233 procedure was achieved. Aiming to recover de bilinearity in the DPV-concentration data array, a
234 shift correction procedure based in correlation shifting method (*i-coshift*) [25-27] was
235 implemented since no shape distortions were observable. Figure 2 shows the DPV signals
236 acquired at three different pH level for several concentrations before and after shifting
237 correction.

**** Figure 2 ****

241 In this way, a bilinear DPV-concentration array at each pH was obtained. Nonetheless,
242 the DPV peak shifts arisen from the pH change were not corrected since the large displacements
243 between signals would hinder the right implementation of a correction strategy and, more
244 importantly, would suppress the selectivity of the second-mode. This phenomenon is a
245 troublesome situation for which solutions were comprehensively analyzed and are described in
246 this work.

3.2.2. Regression model

1
2
3
4 249 To implement the most appropriate regression model, a first evaluation of the trend line
5
6
7 250 describing the relationship between the dependent (DPV signal) and the independent variable
8
9 251 (concentration of the analyte) at every pH was performed. Figure 3 shows the aligned DPV
10
11
12 252 signals for the calibration set (1.0-10.0 mg L⁻¹) acquired at pH 4, 6 and 9.

13
14 253 ***** Figure 3 *****

15 254
16
17 255 A clear difference in the regression trend at the different pH levels is noticeable with the
18
19 256 naked eye. However, to accurately establish a function that explains the regression model for the
20
21
22 257 entire system, it is necessary to perform a thorough evaluation by decomposing the data through
23
24 258 specific chemometric techniques. Hence, experimental data were subjected to MCR-ALS to
25
26 259 explore the empirical behavior of the constituents.
27
28

29 260 30 31 261 *3.3. Data modeling*

32 33 34 262 *3.3.1. MCR-ALS*

35
36 263 MCR-ALS is a wide-spread soft-modelling method that performs bilinear decomposition
37
38
39 264 of a data matrix into two sets of profiles, which comprise relevant physicochemical information
40
41 265 about the constituents of the system under study [17]. The application of this method has been
42
43
44 266 successfully demonstrated in numerous situations proving its potential to reach significant
45
46 267 results. It has been implemented for many purposes, either quantitative analysis [11, 40-42] or
47
48
49 268 descriptive studies allowing unraveling the behavior of chemical or biological processes where
50
51 269 species are totally or partly unknown [43-45]. In this matter, the fact that MCR-ALS can extract
52
53
54 270 the individual contribution of the constituents when no prior information of the system is
55
56 271 available is rather appealing, especially, for investigations of highly complex systems.
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

272 The bilinear decomposition of MCR-ALS is performed under the application of
273 constraints that are implemented during the iterative ALS phase. It is well-documented that if no
274 constraints are implemented, uncountable possible solutions that equivalently represent the
275 system might be obtained. The most common constraints are non-negativity, unimodality and
276 correspondence between species, which relies on chemical principles [46]. However, it has been
277 proved that the application of a full set of constraints helps to diminish the range of feasible
278 solutions, albeit not completely. This phenomenon is known as *rotational ambiguity* [47, 48].

279 With the spread of multivariate data analysis escorted by the evolution of analytical
280 instrumentation, diverse data structures have arisen, that coerced chemometricians to explore
281 new alternatives for the data modeling. Along those lines, MCR-ALS has evolved into a very
282 versatile strategy for the modeling of a wide range of data structures. Even though MCR-ALS is
283 a pure bilinear decomposition model, it has been extended to higher-order multivariate analysis,
284 e.g., third-order data [49-51]. Moreover, it is well-known that first-order calibration models can
285 perform a reliable prediction only in the case that test samples contain the same composition that
286 the calibration samples; however, it has been demonstrated that this drawback can be overcome
287 with the aid of MCR-ALS. Ahmadi et al. have proved the ability of soft-modelling methods in
288 analyzing first-order data sets containing unmodeled components, in which the rotational
289 ambiguity associated to the resolution is minimized by applying specific constraints during
290 iteration [52]. In addition, Esteban's group has demonstrated that the implementation of
291 constraints that model the signal feature shall enhance the performance of the MCR-ALS
292 modeling [53-56].

293 In the present case, pH dimension is the bilinear breaking mode, whereas the
294 concentration mode fulfils the concept of low-rank bilinearity. Thus, to perform a bilinear

1
2
3
4 295 decomposition, the path of Ahmadi work was followed and a *first-order* MCR-ALS strategy was
5
6 296 implemented by unfolding the DPV-pH data to arrays of lower dimension, i.e., an unfolded one-
7
8
9 297 way vector. To achieve the decomposition, a bilinear row-wise concatenated/column-wise
10
11 298 augmented matrix was built. First, a DPV-pH vector was obtained by concatenating the aligned
12
13
14 299 DPV signals of the different pH for each evaluated sample. Then, the concatenated vector
15
16 300 corresponding to each calibration and validation samples were column-wise appended. Figure S2
17
18
19 301 (supplementary material) graphically depicts the data arrangement used for MCR-ALS
20
21 302 decomposition.

22
23
24 303 To start the modeling, initial concentration estimates were obtained by a SIMPLISMA-
25
26 304 like procedure [57] and the number of components was evaluated through singular value
27
28
29 305 decomposition (SVD). The imposed constraints during optimization were non-negativity of
30
31 306 concentration and spectral modes, correspondence among the species and normalization in
32
33 307 concentration. Voltammogram and concentration profiles achieved from the MCR-ALS
34
35
36 308 decomposition for four validation samples containing 4.0 mg mL^{-1} of HIM and calibration data
37
38 309 set are shown in Fig. 4.

39
40
41 310
42
43 311 ***** Figure 4 *****

44
45 312
46
47
48 313 As can be seen in Fig. 4, two components were necessary to describe the behavior of HIM
49
50 314 and one additional component was needed for the samples containing HIS as interferent. These
51
52
53 315 results are in accordance with the afore-mentioned observations demonstrating that the
54
55 316 regression model follows both linear and non-linear behavior against concentration in
56
57
58 317 dependence to the pH. By evaluation of the unfolded voltammogram profiles, it can be noticed
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

318 that the non-linear regression trend prevails at lower pHs, whereas linearity arises with rising the
319 pH values. For the predictive analysis, a pseudo-univariate calibration model was built by using
320 the scores obtained for the factor with linear trend. These scores were plotted against the nominal
321 concentration of the analyte and a least-square regression model was implemented to fit the data.
322 Scores against nominal concentrations are depicted in Fig. 5 and predictive results are
323 summarized in Table 1.

**** Figure 5 ****

327 As can be appreciated, at a higher concentration of the interferent, the contribution of the
328 analyte significantly diminishes (# *Sample 7, 8, 11 and 12* in Table 1). This effect is evidenced
329 by performing a prediction analysis with the scores obtained for the factor with linear regression
330 trend (the scores of the second factor were not considered in this study because of its unusual
331 behavior against concentration). This effect can be the result of two different phenomena. One of
332 them can be related to the possible interaction between the analyte and the interferent, in which
333 the interferent precludes the analyte detection. Besides, it should be considered that in first-order
334 MCR-ALS decomposition, rotational ambiguity is heavily present and gets relevant at higher
335 concentration of the unmodeled component due to the strong signal overlapping [52].

336 Based on these observations, it can be concluded that linear multi-way calibration models
337 cannot be applied and other methodologies that enable the prediction of the analyte in the
338 presence of non-linear regression trend need to be explored.

339
340 3.3.2. U-PLS/RBL

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

341 The unfolded multi-way extension of the renowned PLS method is the U-PLS
342 methodology that performs decomposition to higher dimension arrays. U-PLS it is a multi-way
343 extension of PLS methodology and operates after unfolding the multi-way data arrays into
344 vectors [58]. Those algorithms are applicable on systems showing small deviations of trilinearity,
345 although the second-order advantage is not achieved. The U-PLS methodology consists of
346 performing the classical PLS model calibration with the unfolded calibration data (not including
347 the test samples) using a suitable number of latent variables. If no potential interferents are
348 expected in the test samples, the amplitude of residuals in the prediction step is in the order of
349 the instrumental noise level. Then, the concentration (\hat{y}_i) prediction of the sample is obtained
350 through $\hat{y}_i = \mathbf{t}_i^T \mathbf{v}$, where \mathbf{t}_i is the score vector obtained for the sample data matrix and \mathbf{v} are the
351 regression coefficients acquired from the U-PLS model. However, when interferents are present,
352 the residuals are extraordinarily large in comparison to the instrumental noise and, consequently,
353 this formulation is not suitable for the prediction of the samples. Hence, to overcome this
354 situation, the test sample is subjected to the residual bilinearization (RBL) procedure that enables
355 to separate the signal that is explained by calibration from the contribution of the potential
356 interferents, which means, achieve the second-order advantage [58-60]. To put it succinctly, the
357 residual variance of a test sample is estimated considering the matrix \mathbf{E} which comprise the
358 residuals of the U-PLS model. In the RBL process, the \mathbf{E} matrix is subsequently subjected to
359 SVD decomposition for which results contain information about the interferents. This
360 information that is then added to rebuild the original data matrix. Last, during the residual
361 minimization step, the loadings obtained in the calibration stage remains constant while the
362 scores are adjusted to minimize the residual variance. At the end for the RBL process, when the
363 scores of the test sample are adjusted, the concentration of the analyte can be properly estimated

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

364 [\[61, 62\]](#). The combination of U-PLS and RBL has already been described and demonstrated in
365 the relevant literature [58, 60].

366 In the present case, as it is shown in Fig. 5, the regression model shows a noticeable
367 global non-linear signal behavior. Hence, U-PLS/RBL was implemented because it is one of the
368 most flexible linear second-order multivariate calibration techniques and can cope with mild
369 non-linearities. The calibration step was carried out using the well-known leave-one-out
370 methodology. It is worth noticing that for linear regression system, only one or two PLS factors
371 are necessary to explain the model; however, in the present experimental system, four PLS
372 factors were needed to model the complexity of the data. This fact supports the presence of non-
373 linearity that was observed with the MCR-ALS analysis.

374 The best prediction results were obtained when two RBL components were included in
375 the resolution, which explains the presence of the interferent in the test samples. Table 1
376 comprises the prediction results obtained with the U-PLS/RBL model for the validation samples.
377 These values are better - albeit rather low (\bar{R} % 82 %) - than those obtained from MCR-ALS. It is
378 noticeable that the lower recoveries were obtained for those samples containing the highest
379 amount of the unmodeled component, in accordance with the MCR-ALS results. This conclusion
380 strength the fact that a possible interaction between analyte and interferent is present during
381 detection.

383 3.3.3. Artificial neural networks

384 Artificial neural network (ANN) constitutes a family of multivariate nonparametric
385 regression techniques, which, after a convenient training procedure, are able of learning the
386 correlation of a set of predictor variables with the desired response. The ANN family can be

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

387 subdivided into three groups of techniques: 1) multi-layer perceptron networks (MLP), 2) radial
388 basis functions (RBF), and 3) support vector machines (SVM) [62]. The first two are the most
389 frequently reported in the literature to solve multivariate calibration problems.

Briefly, ANNs contain operating units called neurons, which are arrayed in three layers:
391 1) input, 2) hidden, and 3) output layers. Input and output neurons correspond to the measured
392 signals and the properties predicted by the model, respectively. The hidden nodes represent the
393 computing core. During training or calibration process, each hidden and output node receives
394 weighted contributions, that are then projected on a transfer function to generate a non-linear
395 output. The procedure of learning consists of adjusting the relationship between signals and
396 concentrations by modifying the weights related to the inter-neural connections. Thus, the final
397 output is close to the nominal concentration value for the analyte [20].

In second-order data, the number of original variables comprised in the instrumental
399 signal is usually large and contain redundant information. Then, the information can be
400 compacted into a small number of latent variables. For instance, the principal components (PCs)
401 or scores obtained by computing the explained variance of the unfolded training data can be used
402 as the input layer. When unexpected components are in the test samples, its scores shall not be
403 adequate for the analyte prediction using the trained ANN [63]. Hence, it is necessary to
404 implement a strategy capable to indicate the sample as an outlier, to separate the contribution of
405 the unexpected component from the analyte signal and, then, to build the calibration model to
406 perform the analyte prediction. It has been reported that unfolded PC analysis coupled to RBL
407 (U-PCA/RBL) and subsequent ANN modeling is an excellent alternative to cope with this
408 situation [62, 63]. In this approach, the adjusted score vector t_u obtained at the end of the RBL
409 process is introduced into the ANN network for the subsequent concentration prediction.

1
2
3
4 410 In this work, the number of PCs used as input neurons was four, and two RBL factors
5
6 411 were necessary for the modeling with U-PCA-RBL and subsequent prediction. RBF was chosen
7
8
9 412 to perform the calibration model and the implemented architecture was (4-10-1) for input-
10
11
12 413 hidden-output layers, respectively. The prediction results are shown in Table 1. As can be
13
14 414 appreciated, the performance of U-PCA/RBL-RBF is superior in comparison to the linear
15
16 415 regression methods, yielding excellent recoveries values with a \bar{R} % of 101 % ($s=8$).

18
19 416 Figure 6.A depicts the relationship between the nominal and predicted concentration for
20
21 417 the three chemometric models and the corresponding least-square fitting lines. Figure 6.B shows
22
23
24 418 the elliptical joint confidence region for the slope and the intercept of the linear regression
25
26 419 between the actual and predicted concentration, with a 95% confidence level, for each model.
27
28
29 420 Moreover, Fig 6.A and 6.B indicate the theoretical point and line, respectively, for intercept=0
30
31 421 and slope=1 [64]. Noticing that the ellipse built for U-PCA/RBL-RBF contains the theoretical
32
33 422 expected value for the intercept and slope and, moreover, the fitting line of nominal vs predicted
34
35
36 423 relationship overlaps the theoretical line. These results reinforce the fact that with an in-depth
37
38 424 evaluation of the system behavior leading the use of the proper chemometric tool is possible to
39
40
41 425 leverage the predictive properties of an analytical methodology

42
43 426
44
45 427 ***** Figure 6 *****
46
47

48 428
49
50 429 ***** Table 1 *****
51
52

53 430
54
55 431 **4. Conclusions**
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

432 Second-order based calibration methods have been widely investigated capitalizing on the
433 inherent benefits of the data structure and the decomposition models, demonstrating that second-
434 order advantage is a property that conspires to a high likelihood success in the resolution of
435 systems of varying complexity.

436 In this work, a qualitative and quantitative analysis was performed by implementing
437 parametric and non-parametric methodologies for the determination of histamine in the presence
438 of histidine by differential pulse voltammetry at several pHs as case study.

439 First, MCR-ALS was performed to evaluate the empirical behavior of the constituents. It
440 was proved that first-order data, built from unfolded second-order data, can be solved with the
441 aid of MCR-ALS, allowing to separate the individual contribution of each sample constituent.
442 Based on the acquired results, it was concluded that at least two regression models were
443 necessary to perform the calibration of the analyte, one of which presents a pronounced non-
444 linear behavior. Moreover, it was possible to unravel the presence of a potential interaction
445 between the analyte and the interferent, phenomenon that was reinforced with the results
446 achieved from U-PLS/RBL.

447 On the other hand, U-PCA/RBL combined with RBF modeling significantly outweigh the
448 performance of the parametric models demonstrating the capability to handle non-multilinear
449 data in non-linear regression systems.

450 The results allowed to demonstrate the importance of performing a comprehensive
451 analysis to accurately select the method to implement for the resolution and thus obtain reliable
452 results. The most remarkable accomplishment achieved in this work was the successful
453 implementation of chemometric techniques to bear the foresee difficulty arisen from the large
454 displacement along the potential axis by the pH, which, to the best of our knowledge and belief,

1
2
3
4 455 has not been reported yet. The modeling of non-multilinear data has been a matter of paramount
5
6 456 interest for chemometricians and represents an outstanding challenge in the field of quantitative
7
8
9 457 electroanalytical chemistry. The inception of this research line encourages the development of
10
11
12 458 new chemometric methodologies that lead to a coercive expansion of its range of application.
13

14 459

16 460 **Acknowledgements**

18
19
20 461 This work was supported by the Ministerio de Economía y Competitividad of Spain (Project
21
22 462 CTQ2017-82496-P) and the Junta of Extremadura (GR18041-research Group FQM003), both
23
24 463 co-financed by the European Funds for Regional Development. M.P.V. is grateful to the Junta de
25
26
27 464 Extremadura for a FPI grant (PD16033). MRA and HCG are staff of CONICET and grateful to
28
29 465 CONICET (Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas, Project PIP 2015-0111)
30
31
32 466 and ANPCyT (Agencia Nacional de Promoción Científica y Tecnológica, Project PICT 2017-
33
34 467 0340) for financial support.
35
36

37 468

39
40 469

42 **References**

- 44
45 [1] A.C. Olivieri, Recent advances in analytical calibration with multi-way data, *Anal. Methods*,
46 4 (2012) 1876-1886.
47 [2] A.C. Olivieri, Analytical Advantages of Multivariate Data Processing. One, Two, Three,
48 Infinity?, *Anal. Chem.*, 80 (2008) 5713-5720.
49 [3] A.C. Olivieri, *Introduction to Multivariate Calibration: A Practical Approach*, Springer
50 International Publishing, Cham, 2018.
51 [4] A.C. Olivieri, G.M. Escandar, *Practical Three-Way Calibration*, Elsevier, Waltham, USA,
52 2014.
53 [5] K.S. Booksh, B.R. Kowalski, Theory of Analytical Chemistry, *Anal. Chem.*, 66 (1994)
54 782A-791A.
55 [6] H.A.L. Kiers, A.K. Smilde, Some theoretical results on second-order calibration methods for
56 data with and without rank overlap, *J. Chemom.*, 9 (1995) 179-195.
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

- 1
2
3
4 [7] C. Radulescu, R.L. Olteanu, C. Stih, M. Florescu, R.M. Stirbescu, S.G. Stanescu, C.M.
5 Nicolescu, M. Bumbac, Chemometrics-based vibrational spectroscopy for Juglandis semen
6 extracts investigation, *J. Chemom.*, 34 (2020) e3234.
7
8 [8] M. Albayrak, F. Demirkaya-Miloglu, O. Senol, E. Polatdemir, Design, optimization, and
9 validation of chemometrics-assisted spectrophotometric methods for simultaneous determination
10 of etodolac and thiocolchicoside in pharmaceuticals, *Journal of Analytical Science and*
11 *Technology*, 10 (2019) 16.
12
13 [9] J. Tarrío-Saavedra, M. Francisco-Fernández, S. Naya, J. López-Beceiro, C. Gracia-
14 Fernández, R. Artiaga, Wood identification using pressure DSC data, *J. Chemom.*, 27 (2013)
15 475-487.
16
17 [10] W. Mbogning Feudjio, H. Ghalila, M. Nsangou, Y.G. Mbesse Kongbonga, Y. Majdi,
18 Excitation-emission matrix fluorescence coupled to chemometrics for the exploration of essential
19 oils, *Talanta*, 130 (2014) 148-154.
20
21 [11] M.R. Alcaraz, M.J. Culzoni, H.C. Goicoechea, Enhanced fluorescence sensitivity by
22 coupling yttrium-analyte complexes and three-way fast high-performance liquid chromatography
23 data modeling, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 902 (2016) 50-58.
24
25 [12] M.R. Alcaraz, A. Schwaighofer, H. Goicoechea, B. Lendl, EC-QCL mid-IR transmission
26 spectroscopy for monitoring dynamic changes of protein secondary structure in aqueous solution
27 on the example of β -aggregation in alcohol-denatured α -chymotrypsin, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.*,
28 408 (2016) 3933-3941.
29
30 [13] J.H. Kalivas, 3.01 - Calibration Methodologies, in: S.D. Brown, R. Tauler, B. Walczak,
31 *Comprehensive Chemometrics*, Elsevier, Oxford, 2009, pp. 1-32.
32
33 [14] A.C. Olivieri, G.M. Escandar, H.C. Goicoechea, A.M. de la Peña, Chapter 7 - Unfolded and
34 Multiway Partial Least-Squares with Residual Multilinearization: Fundamentals, in: A. Muñoz
35 de la Peña, H.C. Goicoechea, G.M. Escandar, A.C. Olivieri, *Data Handling in Science and*
36 *Technology*, Elsevier 2015, pp. 347-363.
37
38 [15] J. Ferré, 3.02 - Regression Diagnostics, in: S.D. Brown, R. Tauler, B. Walczak,
39 *Comprehensive Chemometrics*, Elsevier, Oxford, 2009, pp. 33-89.
40
41 [16] R. Bro, PARAFAC. Tutorial and applications, *Chemom. Intell. Lab. Syst.*, 38 (1997) 149-
42 171.
43
44 [17] A. de Juan, S.C. Rutan, R. Tauler, 2.19 - Two-Way Data Analysis: Multivariate Curve
45 Resolution – Iterative Resolution Methods, in: S.D. Brown, R. Tauler, B. Walczak,
46 *Comprehensive Chemometrics*, Elsevier, Oxford, 2009, pp. 325-344.
47
48 [18] K.S. Booksh, B. Bronk, J. Czege, 3.09 - Three-Way Calibration, in: S.D. Brown, R. Tauler,
49 B. Walczak, *Comprehensive Chemometrics*, Elsevier, Oxford, 2009, pp. 379-412.
50
51 [19] F. Marini, 3.14 - Neural Networks, in: S.D. Brown, R. Tauler, B. Walczak, *Comprehensive*
52 *Chemometrics*, Elsevier, Oxford, 2009, pp. 477-505.
53
54 [20] F. Despagne, D.L. Massart, Neural networks in multivariate calibration, *Analyst*, 123 (1998)
55 157R-178R.
56
57 [21] Matlab, The MathWorks Inc., Natick, MA, USA, 2015.
58
59 [22] J. Jaumot, A. De Juan, R. Tauler, MCR-ALS GUI 2.0: New features and applications,
60 *Chemom. Intell. Lab. Syst.*, 140 (2015) 1-12.
61
62 [23] A.C. Olivieri, H.-L. Wu, R.-Q. Yu, MVC2: A MATLAB graphical interface toolbox for
63 second-order multivariate calibration, *Chemom. Intell. Lab. Syst.*, 96 (2009) 246-251.
64
65 [24] A.C. Olivieri, H.C. Goicoechea, F.A. Iñón, MVC1: an integrated MatLab toolbox for first-
order multivariate calibration, *Chemom. Intell. Lab. Syst.*, 73 (2004) 189-197.

- 1
2
3
4 [25] F. Savorani, G. Tomasi, S.B. Engelsen, Alignment of 1D NMR Data using the iCoshift
5 Tool: A Tutorial, *Magnetic Resonance in Food Science: Food for Thought*, The Royal Society of
6 Chemistry 2013, pp. 14-24.
- 7 [26] G. Tomasi, F. Savorani, S.B. Engelsen, icoshift: An effective tool for the alignment of
8 chromatographic data, *J. Chromatogr. A*, 1218 (2011) 7832-7840.
- 9 [27] F. Savorani, G. Tomasi, S.B. Engelsen, icoshift: A versatile tool for the rapid alignment of
10 1D NMR spectra, *J. Magn. Reson.*, 202 (2010) 190-202.
- 11 [28] M. Esteban, M.C. Ariño-Blasco, J.M. Díaz-Cruz, 4.01 - Chemometrics in
12 Electrochemistry☆, in: S.D. Brown, R. Tauler, B. Walczak, *Comprehensive Chemometrics*
13 (Second Edition), Elsevier, Oxford, 2020, pp. 1-31.
- 14 [29] A. Alberich, J.M. Díaz-Cruz, C. Ariño, M. Esteban, Potential shift correction in multivariate
15 curve resolution of voltammetric data. General formulation and application to some experimental
16 systems, *Analyst*, 133 (2008) 112-125.
- 17 [30] J.M. Díaz-Cruz, M. Esteban, C. Ariño, Multivariate Calibration, in: J.M. Díaz-Cruz, M.
18 Esteban, C. Ariño, *Chemometrics in Electroanalysis*, Springer International Publishing, Cham,
19 2019, pp. 87-129.
- 20 [31] A.R. Jalalvand, H.C. Goicoechea, D.N. Rutledge, Applications and challenges of multi-way
21 calibration in electrochemical analysis, *TrAC, Trends Anal. Chem.*, 87 (2017) 32-48.
- 22 [32] I. Cukrowski, J. Havel, Evaluation of Equilibria with a Use of Artificial Neural Networks
23 (ANN): I. Artificial Neural Networks and Experimental Design as a Tool in Electrochemical
24 Data Evaluation for Fully Inert Metal Complexes, *Electroanalysis*, 12 (2000) 1481-1492.
- 25 [33] M. Kooshki, H. Abdollahi, S. Bozorgzadeh, B. Haghighi, Second-order data obtained from
26 differential pulse voltammetry: Determination of tryptophan at a gold nanoparticles decorated
27 multiwalled carbon nanotube modified glassy carbon electrode, *Electrochim. Acta*, 56 (2011)
28 8618-8624.
- 29 [34] A.R. Jalalvand, M.-B. Gholivand, H.C. Goicoechea, T. Skov, Generation of non-multilinear
30 three-way voltammetric arrays by an electrochemically oxidized glassy carbon electrode as an
31 efficient electronic device to achieving second-order advantage: Challenges, and tailored
32 applications, *Talanta*, 134 (2015) 607-618.
- 33 [35] A. Alberich, J.M. Díaz-Cruz, C. Ariño, M. Esteban, Combined use of the potential shift
34 correction and the simultaneous treatment of spectroscopic and electrochemical data by
35 multivariate curve resolution: analysis of a Pb(II)-phytochelatin system. *The Analyst*, 133 (2008)
36 470-477.
- 37 [36] J.M. Díaz Cruz, J. Sanchís, E. Chekmeneva, C. Ariño, M. Esteban, Non-linear multivariate
38 curve resolution analysis of voltammetric pH titrations. *Analyst*, 135 (2010) 1653-1662.
- 39 [37] A.V. Schenone, M.J. Culzoni, A.D. Campiglia, H.C. Goicoechea, Total synchronous
40 fluorescence spectroscopic data modeled with first- and second-order algorithms for the
41 determination of doxorubicin in human plasma, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.*, 405 (2013) 8515-8523.
- 42 [38] A.V. Schenone, A. de Araújo Gomes, M.J. Culzoni, A.D. Campiglia, M.C.U. de Araújo,
43 H.C. Goicoechea, Modeling nonbilinear total synchronous fluorescence data matrices with a
44 novel adapted partial least squares method, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 859 (2015) 20-28.
- 45 [39] P. Puthongkham, S.T. Lee, B.J. Venton, Mechanism of Histamine Oxidation and
46 Electropolymerization at Carbon Electrodes, *Anal. Chem.*, 91 (2019) 8366-8373.
- 47 [40] M.R. Alcaraz, A.V. Schenone, M.J. Culzoni, H.C. Goicoechea, Modeling of second-order
48 spectrophotometric data generated by a pH-gradient flow injection technique for the
49 determination of doxorubicin in human plasma, *Microchem. J.*, 112 (2014) 25-33.
- 50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

- 1
2
3
4 [41] M.R. Alcaraz, L. Vera Candiotti, M.J. Culzoni, H.C. Goicoechea, Ultrafast quantitation of
5 six quinolones in water samples by second-order capillary electrophoresis data modeling with
6 multivariate curve resolution–alternating least squares, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.*, 406 (2014) 2571-
7 2580.
8
9 [42] C.M. Teglia, S.M. Azcarate, M.R. Alcaráz, H.C. Goicoechea, M.J. Culzoni, Exploiting the
10 synergistic effect of concurrent data signals: Low-level fusion of liquid chromatographic with
11 dual detection data, *Talanta*, 186 (2018) 481-488.
12 [43] M.R. Alcaraz, A. Aguirre, H.C. Goicoechea, M.J. Culzoni, S.E. Collins, Resolution of
13 intermediate surface species by combining modulated infrared spectroscopy and chemometrics,
14 *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1049 (2019) 38-46.
15 [44] A. Schwaighofer, M.R. Alcaraz, L. Lux, B. Lendl, pH titration of β -lactoglobulin monitored
16 by laser-based Mid-IR transmission spectroscopy coupled to chemometric analysis, *Spectrochim.*
17 *Acta A Mol. Biomol. Spectrosc.*, 226 (2020) 117636.
18 [45] R. Brasca, A.-M. Kelterer, M. Maeder, M.R. Alcaraz, M.J. Culzoni, Quantum chemical
19 computation-based strategy for alternating least squares initialization in multivariate curve
20 resolution analysis of spectral-pH data, *Microchem. J.*, 140 (2018) 183-188.
21 [46] R. Tauler, M. Maeder, A. de Juan, 2.24 - Multiset Data Analysis: Extended Multivariate
22 Curve Resolution, in: S.D. Brown, R. Tauler, B. Walczak, *Comprehensive Chemometrics*,
23 Elsevier, Oxford, 2009, pp. 473-505.
24 [47] M.R. Alcaraz, M.J. Culzoni, G.A. Ibañez, V.A. Lozano, A.C. Olivieri, On second-order
25 calibration based on multivariate curve resolution in the presence of highly overlapped profiles,
26 *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1096 (2020) 53-60.
27 [48] A. Golshan, H. Abdollahi, S. Beyramysoltan, M. Maeder, K. Neymeyr, R. Rajkó, M.
28 Sawall, R. Tauler, A review of recent methods for the determination of ranges of feasible
29 solutions resulting from soft modelling analyses of multivariate data, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 911
30 (2016) 1-13.
31 [49] M.R. Alcaraz, G.G. Siano, M.J. Culzoni, A. Muñoz de la Peña, H.C. Goicoechea, Modeling
32 four and three-way fast high-performance liquid chromatography with fluorescence detection
33 data for quantitation of fluoroquinolones in water samples, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 809 (2014) 37-46.
34 [50] M. Montemurro, G.G. Siano, M.R. Alcaraz, H.C. Goicoechea, Third order
35 chromatographic-excitation–emission fluorescence data: Advances, challenges and prospects in
36 analytical applications, *TrAC, Trends Anal. Chem.*, 93 (2017) 119-133.
37 [51] A. Malik, R. Tauler, Extension and application of multivariate curve resolution-alternating
38 least squares to four-way quadrilinear data–obtained in the investigation of pollution patterns on
39 Yamuna River, India—A case study, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 794 (2013) 20-28.
40 [52] G. Ahmadi, R. Tauler, H. Abdollahi, Multivariate calibration of first-order data with the
41 correlation constrained MCR-ALS method, *Chemom. Intell. Lab. Syst.*, 142 (2015) 143-150.
42 [53] J. Mendieta, M.S. Díaz-Cruz, R. Tauler, M. Esteban, Application of Multivariate Curve
43 Resolution to Voltammetric Data: II. Study of Metal-Binding Properties of the Peptides, *Anal.*
44 *Biochem.*, 240 (1996) 134-141.
45 [54] M.S. Díaz-Cruz, J. Mendieta, R. Tauler, M. Esteban, Multivariate Curve Resolution of
46 Cyclic Voltammetric Data: Application to the Study of the Cadmium-Binding Properties of
47 Glutathione, *Anal. Chem.*, 71 (1999) 4629-4636.
48 [55] S. Cavanillas, J.M. Díaz-Cruz, C. Ariño, M. Esteban, Parametric signal fitting by gaussian
49 peak adjustment: A new multivariate curve resolution method for non-bilinear voltammetric
50 measurements, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 689 (2011) 198-205.
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

- 1
2
3
4 [56] S. Cavanillas, N. Serrano, J.M. Díaz-Cruz, C. Ariño, M. Esteban, Parametric Signal Fitting
5 by Gaussian Peak Adjustment: implementation of 2D transversal constraints and its application
6 for the determination of pKa and complexation constants by differential pulse voltammetry,
7 Analyst, 138 (2013) 2171-2180.
8
9 [57] W. Windig, J. Guilment, Interactive self-modeling mixture analysis, Anal. Chem., 63 (1991)
10 1425-1432.
11 [58] A.C. Olivieri, On a versatile second-order multivariate calibration method based on partial
12 least-squares and residual bilinearization: Second-order advantage and precision properties, J.
13 Chemom., 19 (2005) 253-265.
14 [59] G.M. Escandar, H.C. Goicoechea, A. Muñoz de la Pena, A.C. Olivieri, Second- and higher-
15 order data generation and calibration: a tutorial, Anal. Chim. Acta, 806 (2014) 8-26.
16 [60] J. Öhman, P. Geladi, S. Wold, Residual bilinearization. Part 1: Theory and algorithms, J.
17 Chemom., 4 (1990) 79-90.
18 [61] A. de Araújo Gomes, M.R. Alcaraz, H.C. Goicoechea, M.C. Araújo, The Successive
19 Projections Algorithm for interval selection in trilinear partial least-squares with residual
20 bilinearization, Anal. Chim. Acta, 811 (2014) 13-22.
21 [62] A. García-Reiriz, P.C. Damiani, M.J. Culzoni, H.C. Goicoechea, A.C. Olivieri, A versatile
22 strategy for achieving the second-order advantage when applying different artificial neural
23 networks to non-linear second-order data: Unfolded principal component analysis/residual
24 bilinearization, Chemom. Intell. Lab. Syst., 92 (2008) 61-70.
25 [63] A.C. Olivieri, A combined artificial neural network/residual bilinearization approach for
26 obtaining the second-order advantage from three-way non-linear data, J. Chemom., 19 (2005)
27 615-624.
28 [64] J. Riu, F.X. Rius, Method comparison using regression with uncertainties in both axes,
29 TrAC, Trends Anal. Chem., 16 (1997) 211-216.
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

Figure 1. (A) Differential pulse voltammograms obtained at GEC in BRB solution containing of 5.0 mg L⁻¹ HIM at the pH range of 4-9 (from cyan to red lines) and the (B) Differential pulse voltammograms obtained at GEC registered for concentrations of 1.0-10.0 mg L⁻¹ HIM at pH 6.

Figure 2. (A) Original and (B) aligned DPV signals acquired for several concentrations of HIM at pH 4 (cyan) 6 (purple) and 9 (red).

Figure 3. Aligned DPV signals of 1.0 mg L^{-1} (solid cyan line) and 10.0 mg L^{-1} (solid red line) of HIM at pH 4, 6 and 9. DPV signals of 2.5 mg L^{-1} (dotted line), 5.0 mg L^{-1} (dash-dotted line) and 7.5 mg L^{-1} (dashed line) mg L^{-1} of HIM are shown. Grey bars indicate the current of $0.1 \text{ } \mu\text{A}$. Inset: maximum current intensity against concentration at pH 4 (cyan) 6 (purple) and 9 (red).

Figure 4. (A) Concentration and (B) unfolded voltammogram profiles acquired after MCR-ALS decomposition of DVP-pH signals. The first six samples correspond to validation samples containing 4.0 mg L^{-1} HIM (empty red and full cyan circles) and 25.0 , 5.0 and 15.0 mg L^{-1} HIS (grey triangles) in duplicate, respectively.

Figure 5. MCR-ALS concentration scores obtained from the calibration signals of HIM against nominal concentration. Scores of first (full cyan dots) and second (empty red dots) MCR-ALS factors show the linear and nonlinear regression trends, respectively. Dashed cyan line and dash-dotted red line are the fitted lines through linear and quadratic function, respectively.

Figure 6. (A) Nominal against predicted concentrations of HIM (in mg mL^{-1}) and the corresponding least-square fitting lines. (B) Elliptical joint of confidence region (95% confidence level) for the slope and the intercept of the linear regression between the nominal and the predicted concentrations of HIM. MCR-ALS (dotted red line), U-PLS/RBL (dash-dotted blue line) and U-PCA/RBL-RBF (dashed green line). Results for MCR-ALS are in red, U-PLS/RBL in blue and U-PCA/RBL-RBF are in green. The theoretical regression line (A) and the ideal point (B) (slope=1, intercept=0) are shown in black.

Table 1. Recovery results obtained from validation samples using parametric and nonparametric methodologies.

# Sample	HIM (mg L ⁻¹) ^a			HIS ^b (mg L ⁻¹)	
	Nominal	Predicted			
		MCR/ALS	UPLS/RBL		U-PCA/RBL - RBF
1	2.0	2.1 (105)	2.4 (120)	2.2 (110)	25.0
2	2.0	2.2 (110)	2.1 (105)	1.8 (90)	25.0
3	2.0	1.3 (65)	1.7 (85)	1.9 (95)	5.0
4	2.0	1.5 (75)	1.8 (90)	2.1 (105)	5.0
5	2.0	1.3 (65)	1.6 (75)	2.3 (115)	15.0
6	2.0	1.3 (65)	1.5 (74)	1.7 (85)	15.0
7	4.0	2.2 (55)	3.0 (75)	4.4 (110)	25.0
8	4.0	2.4 (60)	3.1 (78)	4.6 (115)	25.0
9	4.0	2.9 (73)	3.2 (80)	3.9 (98)	5.0
10	4.0	2.8 (70)	3.1 (78)	3.9 (98)	5.0
11	4.0	1.8 (45)	2.8 (70)	4.1 (103)	15.0
12	4.0	1.9 (48)	2.8 (70)	4.1 (103)	15.0
13	8.0	5.7 (71)	5.9 (70)	7.5 (94)	25.0
14	8.0	5.8 (73)	6.0 (75)	8.1 (101)	25.0
15	8.0	5.3 (66)	6.2 (78)	7.9 (99)	5.0
16	8.0	5.4 (68)	6.8 (85)	8.3 (104)	5.0
17	8.0	5.4 (68)	6.7 (84)	7.8 (98)	15.0
18	8.0	5.7 (71)	6.6 (83)	8.2 (103)	15.0
$\bar{R}\%$ ^c		70 (s=16)	82 (s=12)	101 (s=8)	

^a Recoveries (%) are between parenthesis

^b HIS as an interferent

^c Mean recovery in %

Table 1. Recovery results obtained from validation samples using parametric and nonparametric methodologies.

# Sample	HIM (mg L ⁻¹) ^a				HIS ^b (mg L ⁻¹)
	Nominal	Predicted			
		MCR/ALS	UPLS/RBL	U-PCA/RBL - RBF	
1	2.0	2.1 (105)	2.4 (120)	2.2 (110)	25.0
2	2.0	2.2 (110)	2.1 (105)	1.8 (90)	25.0
3	2.0	1.3 (65)	1.7 (85)	1.9 (95)	5.0
4	2.0	1.5 (75)	1.8 (90)	2.1 (105)	5.0
5	2.0	1.3 (65)	1.6 (75)	2.3 (115)	15.0
6	2.0	1.3 (65)	1.5 (74)	1.7 (85)	15.0
7	4.0	2.2 (55)	3.0 (75)	4.4 (110)	25.0
8	4.0	2.4 (60)	3.1 (78)	4.6 (115)	25.0
9	4.0	2.9 (73)	3.2 (80)	3.9 (98)	5.0
10	4.0	2.8 (70)	3.1 (78)	3.9 (98)	5.0
11	4.0	1.8 (45)	2.8 (70)	4.1 (103)	15.0
12	4.0	1.9 (48)	2.8 (70)	4.1 (103)	15.0
13	8.0	5.7 (71)	5.9 (70)	7.5 (94)	25.0
14	8.0	5.8 (73)	6.0 (75)	8.1 (101)	25.0
15	8.0	5.3 (66)	6.2 (78)	7.9 (99)	5.0
16	8.0	5.4 (68)	6.8 (85)	8.3 (104)	5.0
17	8.0	5.4 (68)	6.7 (84)	7.8 (98)	15.0
18	8.0	5.7 (71)	6.6 (83)	8.2 (103)	15.0
$\bar{R}\%$ ^c		70 (s=16)	82 (s=12)	101 (s=8)	

^a Recoveries (%) are between parenthesis

^b HIS as an interferent

^c Mean recovery in %

Figure 1
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Figure 2

[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Figure 3
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Figure 4
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Figure 5
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Figure 6
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Exploring the potential of combining chemometric approaches to model non-linear multi-way data – A case study

Mónica Palomino-Vasco¹, Nielen Mora-Díez¹, [María Isabel Rodríguez-Cáceres](#), [María](#)

[Isabel Acedo-Valenzuela](#), Mirta R. Alcaraz^{2,3*} and Héctor C. Goicoechea^{2,3}

¹ *Department of Analytical Chemistry and Research Institute on Water, Climate Change and Sustainability (IACYS), University of Extremadura, Badajoz, 06006, Spain*

² *Laboratorio de Desarrollo Analítico y Quimiometría (LADAQ), Cátedra de Química Analítica I, Facultad de Bioquímica y Ciencias Biológicas, Universidad Nacional del Litoral, Ciudad Universitaria, Santa Fe (S3000ZAA), Argentina*

³ *Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas (CONICET), Godoy Cruz 2290 CABA (C1425FQB), Argentina.*

Corresponding author:

*E-mail: malcaraz@fcb.unl.edu.ar (M.R. Alcaraz). Tel.: +54 342 4575206 x190

Figure S-1. Example of the baseline correction employing GPES. Voltammogram without any treatment in blue, and after baseline correction in red.

Figure S-2. Data arrangement for MCR-ALS resolution. Cal 1- n are de DPV-pH signals corresponding to the calibration samples and Val 1 is the corresponding signal of validation samples. (SUPPLEMENTARIA?)